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DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

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PRACTISING ENGLISH USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY

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***Abstract:** Digital technology provides children with a great number of opportunities to practise their English.*

***Key words:** English, communication, approach, love, hate, learning, environment.*

Children growing up in a supportive digital environment are learning the skills that they will need for their future studies and careers. Here are some fantastic ways you and your child can use technology together to practise English. Parents often feel unsure about their child using mobile phones and computers. You may like to read our Frequently Asked Questions: How to use technology for learning.

Learning English with digital storytelling

Digital tools can be a great way for learners to use their language in fun and creative ways. It gives them some control over their own learning, by giving them a chance to be in the director's chair!

Learning tip Help your child bring their stories to life. There are loads of great storytelling tools where children can create their own fairy tales, comic strips, puppet shows, 3D popup books or cartoons.

Here are some apps you could try:

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- **Make your own e-book:** Create your own drawings, record your voice, add photos, music, video and text (Book Creator for iOS, Android and Windows).
- **Make your own cartoon:** Choose your characters and your setting, then move the characters around and voice your own cartoon (Toontastic for iOS and Android).

Games and apps

Our free games and apps are designed to help learners improve their English in a fun way. We provide lots of great learning tips in our article: Learn English through games.

The games industry is huge – it's bigger now than the music industry or the movie box office! There are all sorts of different types of games and apps, from puzzles and quizzes, to action games, to solitaire and Sudoku. We've even run some very successful pilots using apps like dubsmash where children record themselves singing in English over a pop song. Try exploring and learning together!

Learning tip Encourage the whole family to take part in an app challenge. Ask each family member to download one free language-learning app onto their tablet or phone. You may want to provide a few key search words. For example: 'Learn English kids', 'English speaking practice'. Alternatively, check out some of these top-rated apps that promote language and reading. Ask each family member to talk about their app. They could show how it works and say what they like about it. Then have a vote to decide which app is the family favourite. 955

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Learning English with social media

Social media provides lots of opportunities to interact in English. Find out more in our article: Learn English through social media. *Learning tip for 13–18 year olds*
The Cambridge English Facebook page has daily tips, quizzes, activities and advice for learning English. It supports students from all over the world to discuss things in English.

Still feeling a bit unsure?

Technology is messy. Our main piece of advice is to embrace the uncertainty, and remember we are ALL learners. The exciting part of digital technology is that children, parents and teachers are all learning about digital technologies together, at the same time. Technology is constantly changing and improving. It's OK to try, try and try again. Children will learn that using technology is about exploring, discovering, experimenting, creating and being open-minded to new opportunities.

Learning English with blogs and vlogs

Blogs are a bit like an online journal. Your child can write about their interests, ideas, wishes, humour and anything else they think about. Research suggests that blogging helps schoolchildren practise writing. Students tend to write more in blogs – they are writing for a real audience and a real purpose. Check out these blogging sites for children, which can be monitored by parents. Alternatively, if your child would prefer to practise their speaking skills, they could tell you about their ideas and record it in a video (vlog). *Learn Learning tip for 5–12 year olds*
Your child might enjoy telling you their 'news'. With your help, they could turn this into their own English 'diary' blog.

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- Ask your child to tell you something about their day. This can be in English or in your own language.
- Together, write down the key words/sentences in English.
- Now, ask your child to upload a picture to show what they did.
- Then, ask your child to read the key words/sentences back to you in English.

Your child might also enjoy collecting these pictures on a wall in their bedroom, or making them into a mini-book to read later on.

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